

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME:** Henrici**FIRST NAME:** Johanna**PROGRAM CODE:** PHGH**COURSE CODE :** ACA-401D**PERIOD NUMBER:** 1**INSTRUCTOR:** Dr. Gulma**Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium

The author used the following software: MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

BASIC ASPECTS OF ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

When it comes to academic writing, there are some basic aspects and rules which should be taken into account. The first period of the course Academic writing at EUCLID University gives an overview about the main points.

2) BASIC ASPECTS OF ACADEMIC WRITING

In the first coursepack of the course Academic Writing (EUCLID 2019) Prof. Cleenewerck and Dr. Gulma introduce the main important aspects of academic writing:

To be able to start essay writing it is important to define the essay question and construct the initial plan. It is critical that the basis of academic writing is researching the topic as this allows you to develop a hypothesis and ideas for its answer. “A feature of most academic writing is that it draws on the work of other writers and researchers” (EUCLID 2019, 2). After having done the research the next step is to organize your ideas and write your essay in the common structure: introduction, body and conclusion. An academic essay must contain references. The final step would be to edit your essay in the end.

Through using citations and references plagiarism is avoided. “Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information” (EUCLID, 2019, 5). This is very important as it is unethical to take someone’s ideas without recognizing them and “is a serious academic offense that can have serious consequences” (ibid.). There are different ways of citing, for example in-text citation or

footnote referencing. In any case a list of works cited should be provided at the end of the paper or book.

Another important aspect of academic writing is the existence of different style guides. While many different style guides exist, they all have in common that they want to ensure “that the writing style is consistent and so guidelines are usually published to allow more than one author to contribute while ensuring that the finished piece does not necessarily carry the personal style of the writer” (EUCLID 2019, 24). A style guide can address different aspects, e.g. the use of headings, abbreviations, spelling etc. More in detail the authors are describing the Chicago Style, also known as “Turabian style” (EUCLID 2019, 44). This style guide is, among other aspects, giving advice about how to deal with abbreviations, capitalization, numbers and quotations.

Prof. Cleenewerck and Dr. Gulma are also giving some rules of thumb for writing papers. They are for example advising to state the main thesis of the paper in the beginning and stay focused throughout the whole essay. Additionally, they are suggesting supporting assertions and take the views one is discussing seriously.

Another focus of the authors is lying on the “basic differences and influences of change” (EUCLID 2019, 27) between American and British English. Between American and British English there exist some general categories of differences: Words could be pronounced differently, although they are spelled in the same way – and the other way round. There might be differences in the meaning of the same words, differences in grammar and syntax, regional variations and some more. “Most divergence can be ascribed to differing national histories and cultural development [...], and the way in which the two national variants have changed correspondingly” (ibid.).

Prof. Cleenewerck and Dr. Gulma are finishing their introduction by providing two tables showing common Latin abbreviations and expressions. “Latin abbreviations are appropriate in footnotes, bibliographies, and informal writing (e.g., the information in parentheses)” (EUCLID 2019, 56).

3) MY REACTION

Academic writing requires the knowledge of some basic aspects. This includes the knowledge about how to start and structure an essay, the importance of citations, the usefulness of a style guide as well as the awareness of the differences between American and British English.

In my studies of psychology and public health I was already introduced to the basic aspects and had to apply them in several projects. What was really interesting for me as a German was the described predominance of American English nowadays. In Germany in academia the focus is mainly on British English and also children are educated using British English.

In my recent work as a study administrator I am used to work with scientific study protocols. In these protocols there is also a certain style guide applied and abbreviations are used. It takes some time to get used to this kind of writing and to be able to understand the complex content. As my work does not contain academic writing itself, I am happy and excited to improve these skills during my PhD. This is why the first coursepack was a very helpful start for me. It made me aware of the basic aspects of academic writing and where to pay attention to.

For me as an English non-native speaker it is of course a challenge to do research and academic writing in a foreign language. Therefore, the section about the differences between British and American English was very interesting and also helpful. But also, all the other parts helped me very much in understanding the whole process of academic writing.

4) CONCLUSION

Academic writing is a very special type of writing and presumes the knowledge of basic conventions and aspects of academic writing. A key feature of academic writing is that it draws on the work of other writers and researchers. This is why the first step is always to make a sufficient literature review and to become an “expert” of the research which is done so far in the area you plan to do some writing. This goes along with appreciating the work other writers and researchers did and contribute your respect with citations of their work. One piece of academic writing needs to be embedded in its context and that is also what it makes so exciting as you can see the development of theories, opinions, data concerning a certain topic. This development might be shaped by external happenings, history and events and makes academic writing more than just a piece of writing. The process of academic writing presumes more than good writing skills, but also the ability to get an oversight about a research situation quite quickly, stick to guides and conventions and to be creative and innovative through contributing a new piece of research to the whole “research universe”.

To sum up for me the coursepack was very helpful to be aware of the most important aspects of academic writing and is a good source to have a look at during the whole PhD process and its corresponding assignments. Especially the differences between American and British English, but also the information about the “Turabian Style” and the common abbreviations will probably guide my work during the whole course. It was a good start into the program and made me clear what academic writing really means and why it is my wish to improve my skills in academic writing and doing research.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma, 2nd ed. 2019. *ACA-401/ACA401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.